

OVERVIEW OF THE IFACT-MP PROJECT: A EUROPEAN IODINE FED ADVANCED CUSP FIELD THRUSTER FOR MID-POWER

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ABSTRACT:

The iFACT-MP project aims to develop a 3–5 kW hybrid propulsion subsystem featuring an electric thruster configuration that utilizes an iodine-fed anode alongside a krypton-fed cathode. In parallel, a secondary development path focused on iodine-fed cathodes utilizing enhanced C12A7 emitters. Furthermore, other critical technologies for the subsystem were developed, such as the iodine fluidic chain, consisting of tank, flow regulator and heated pipework, as well as a breadboard PPU to manage the control loops and automated procedures. For system characterization, an in-situ optical mass flow meter was developed and an iodine-compatible vacuum facility equipped for high-power thrust and plume diagnostics was built. Following major milestones being achieved through component validation and coupling testing, the project is moving into a final endurance test campaign to verify system reliability and performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The satellite industry shows an increasingly growing demand for high-efficiency propulsion to maximize payload capacity and multi-launch capability. While kilowatt-class Electric Propulsion (EP) is essential for larger spacecraft, the high cost of xenon —

exceeding €20,000/kg — and Europe's dependence on external noble gas suppliers present significant strategic and economic vulnerabilities.

Iodine emerges as a high-performance, sustainable alternative, offering an ionization potential and atomic mass comparable to xenon. Its high storage density of 4.9 kg/L and low vapor pressure eliminate the need for high-pressure tanks, allowing for conformal vessel geometries and simplified ground handling. By transitioning to a solid propellant, launch-site loading procedures are removed, which together with the low propellant cost significantly reduce mission costs.

The iFACT-MP project has addressed this transition by developing Europe's first 3–5 kW iodine-fed propulsion subsystem. This effort includes upscaling Advanced Cusp Field Thruster (ACFT) technology, engineering a complete iodine fluidic chain, and implementing a breadboard Power Processing Unit (PPU) for autonomous control. In the pursuit of a fully iodine fed EP chain, an iodine-fed neutraliser has been investigated, requiring improvements to the C12A7 emitter ceramics. Furthermore, an in-situ optical flow meter and a specialized iodine-compatible vacuum facility have been developed. The project will culminate in a 500-hour endurance test to validate the subsystem's long-term operational readiness. The building blocks for the iFACT-MP project are shown in Fig. 1-1.

Figure 1-1: The building blocks of the iFACT-MP project.

2. DEVELOPMENT STATUS

The following chapter will give an overview of the work performed by each member of the consortium, including Airbus Friedrichshafen (FHN), Airbus Toulouse (TLS), Fraunhofer IKTS, Airbus Elancourt (ELC), Aerospazio, University of Pisa, and the European Aerospace Science Network (EASN).

2.1. Airbus FHN: Management, Thruster and Cathode Development

The thruster unit comprises the up-scaled ACFT, a hollow cathode neutralizer, and a triangular mounting bracket engineered to meet mechanical and thermal loads. The fully assembled thruster unit is shown in Fig. 2-1.

Figure 2-1: The iFACT-MP thruster unit, integrated in the Airbus FHN test facility for the initial krypton testing.

The propulsion subsystem initially underwent validation using xenon and krypton with Airbus FHN ground support equipment, demonstrating stable operation up to 3.2 kW at a 500 V discharge voltage.

Subsequent iodine testing was conducted as a full coupling test, utilizing the Airbus ELC breadboard PPU and Airbus TLS iodine fluidic chain, which achieved a peak power of 3.6 kW. However, anode current oscillations were observed at discharge voltages exceeding 300 V. These instabilities

appear to be a phenomenon specific to iodine and will be further investigated during the 500-h endurance test at Aerospazio. The test campaign was initialized, but interrupted due to an electrical fault in the protective circuit of the PPU. Further information about the design, performance characterization, and test campaigns of the thruster unit are provided in a separate proceeding by Sütterlin [1].

Lastly, iodine-fed cathode prototypes were developed in parallel using advanced C12A7 emitters, provided by Fraunhofer IKTS, in both planar and hollow cathode configurations [2]. Both cathodes were ignited heaterless, as the corrosive iodine environment and high emissivity of the graphite used for the structure proved to make a heated ignition challenging with respect to the reliability and lifetime. While stable operation on krypton validated the underlying thermal and mechanical designs, iodine testing yielded significant instabilities, as shown in Fig. 2-2.

Figure 2-2: Test results of the iodine-fed planar cathode prototype, with a dual feeding enabling krypton and iodine testing. Only short phases of iodine operation are achieved.

Figure 2-3: Hollow cathode installed for acceptance ignition cycling.

Due to the low maturity level and difficulties of the experimental iodine fed cathode, the fallback solution of a krypton-fed hollow cathode was implemented in the thruster unit design.

Due to the high-power level, such an architecture is still attractive due to the low propellant flow split, and the low relative mass of the additional feeding compared to the total propellant mass. Additionally, the krypton-fed cathode achieves high power efficiency, was successfully acceptance tested for a total duration of 100 h and 100 cycles (Fig. 2-3), and underwent mechanical and environmental testing.

2.2. Airbus TLS: Fluidics Development and Systems Engineering

The subsystem employs a direct-feed architecture, where the thruster and cathode are integrated with dedicated propellant storage, flow regulation, and control electronics. The system was engineered to encompass LEO/MEO constellations and high-power GEO applications; a common design envelope across Airbus EP applications. It covers the functionality, performance and expected environments (mechanical, thermal, radiation) as well as design-to-manufacture type of requirements (M&P, PA/QA).

The iodine fluidic chain consists of an Iodine Storage Tank (IST) and a Feed System (IFS) connected by flexible heated piping to the thruster. The IST utilizes a metallic liner with heaters for propellant sublimation. The IFS employs flow regulation technology with integrated heating to maintain the iodine in a gaseous state. The tank and associated thermal hardware are an assembly of COTS, while a supplier was selected to manufacture and develop the iodine feed regulator in accordance with operational requirements.

The krypton fluidic system (KFS) was developed based on a flight representative regulator and is operated via a bang-bang regulation scheme.

Both the IST, IFS, and KST were successfully tested separately at the Airbus TLS facility with krypton, while initial iodine loading and testing with the thruster unit was performed in Airbus FHN. In December 2025 the teams of Airbus FHN, TLS, ELC and University of Pisa met at the newly developed Aerospazio facility to install the setup for the final endurance test. The thruster unit, iodine fluidic chain, and MFM were installed on the thrust balance and wrapped with MLI to ensure homogeneous heating of the iodine fluidic path. The test set-up is shown in Fig. 2-4.

Figure 2-4: Coupling test set-up at Aerospazio, featuring the thruster unit, iodine and krypton fluidic chain, and mass flow meter. All fluidic units have been thermally managed by the PPU, and insulated with MLI blankets.

The major outcomes from the initial functional test of the IST and IFS at the Airbus TLS facility, followed by the coupling tests at Airbus FHN and Aerospazio test facility, includes:

- Validation of the flow management architecture, confirming that mass flow can be precisely controlled via temperature and pressure gradients from the storage tank to the thruster.
- Verification of the tank design, specifically the effectiveness of radiative heat exchange for incremental propellant filling and controlled iodine sublimation.
- Successful integration of the breadboard PPU with the fluidic chain, which demonstrated stable power delivery and closed-loop regulation of all heated propellant lines.
- Characterization of system response, establishing a clear correlation between thermal control inputs and thruster discharge current.
- Demonstration of IFS capabilities, ensuring reliable iodine flow from initial start-up to low power steady state thrust.
- No observed instances of iodine leakage or propellant clogging throughout the test campaign.
- Validation KFS bang-bang regulation scheme.

2.3. Fraunhofer IKTS: Calcium Aluminate Electride Development

In order to achieve stable and continuous electron emission from the emitter ceramic in the cathode, its thermal stability is important. Historically, C12A7 electride suffered from localized self-heating, leading to partial melting and subsequent performance degradation. To address this, Fraunhofer IKTS investigated various dopants to elevate the material's melting point. While several dopants induced secondary phase formations or negligible thermal shifts, Nb₂O₅ doping successfully increased the melting point by approximately 50 K, reaching the target threshold of 1450°C. The work chain is shown in Fig. 2-5.

Figure 2-5: Flow chart of the preparation of C12A7:e ceramic as electron emitting ceramic in cathodes.

In addition to improving the melting point, it was also demonstrated that the current density is not significantly affected by the doping. Therefore, it can

be concluded that higher current densities can be achieved with C12A7 than with LaB₆. The current density plot for different doping is shown in Fig. 2-6.

Figure 2-6: Current density depending on the temperature of for LaB₆ and doped and none-doped C12A7:e-.

To maximize emitter surface area, the project developed a specialized manufacturing process for C12A7 foils. This involved casting a particle-filled tape from C12A7 powder, which was then molded onto structured glass plates under controlled heating. These structures remained stable throughout the debinding and sintering phases. The resulting thin, formable foils allow for complex geometries — such as emitters for hollow cathodes — and enable the lamination of C12A7 with different compositions to e.g., optimise between thermionic properties at the emitting surface, and thermal and electrical conductivity at the contacting surface. The structuring process is shown in Fig. 2-7.

Figure 2-7: Visualization of structured surface of the C12A7 emitter ceramic before and after sintering.

Despite these material advancements, integrated testing of iodine-fed planar and hollow cathode configurations using both LaB₆ and C12A7 emitters failed to meet the required stability and performance benchmarks (as indicated by Fig. 2-2). Consequently, the project transitioned to the baseline krypton-fed cathode for the integrated thruster unit to ensure operational reliability.

2.4. Airbus ELC: Breadboard PPU Development

The iFACT-MP breadboard PPU was developed to emulate both flight-representative power electronics and the satellite-level control logic required for autonomous mission management. Engineered for the 3–5 kW power class with discharge capabilities up to 800 V, the system architecture integrates power distribution, high-accuracy measurement

racks, and a centralized control computer. The breadboard PPU comprises:

- The mains rack, which is used to distribute the power inside the PPU breadboard.
- A self-test rack, which is used to automatically check the behaviour of the PPU breadboard before connecting it to the thruster.
- A safety cassette, which includes protections for all elements of the system.
- Harnesses to interface with the fluidics system and the vacuum chamber containing the thruster to characterize.
- A computer containing all the software used to drive the thruster, the thermal control and the fluidic system, including a graphical interface, to facilitate the communication between the operator and the previous elements.

Validation of the PPU began with functional testing using thruster and fluidic simulators, ensuring control loop stability before hardware integration. Initial coupling tests with the iodine thruster were successfully conducted in Airbus FHN in September 2025, followed by shipment to the Aerospazio facility in December for full subsystem checkouts. By early 2026, integrated software adaptations were implemented to refine regulation parameters, culminating in a successful thruster ignition in February. Following the repair and recertification of the safety hardware, damaged during a test with the thruster, the PPU breadboard was repaired and is awaiting the final 500-hour endurance campaign.

The breadboard PPU, together with some of the members of the consortium, are visible in Fig. 2-8.

Figure 2-8: Integration of the full subsystem at Aerospazio.

2.5. Aerospazio: Iodine Test Facility Development

The iodine vacuum facility is built around a double vessel configuration: the main chamber size is in the medium class according to the Aerospazio

Tecnologie classification, with a nominal diameter of 2.4 m and a length of 6 m. The auxiliary chamber, allowing operations on the test set-up without breaking the high vacuum condition in the main chamber, has a nominal diameter of 0.8 m and length of 1.4 m and is coupled with the main chamber through a gate valve with a nominal diameter of 65 cm. The facility is shown in Fig. 2-9 and Fig. 2-10.

To isolate the noisiest part of the system and maximize the cleanliness of the section dedicated to the experiment, the vacuum chamber is housed halfway between two rooms: the Laboratory, where the actual test is set up, and the Technical Room used to house primary pumps, cryogenic compressors, and various auxiliary systems.

All the equipment exposed to the vacuum environment inside the vessels is customized to withstand the effects of ionized iodine, well known from the previous iFACT project, through appropriate selection of corrosion resistant materials and surface treatments.

The test facility is equipped with a dedicated iodine pumping system, a secondary recovery chamber to remove iodine at the end of the test, and a cryogenic filter to prevent residual iodine from reaching the primary pumps. All these secondary systems, powered by liquid nitrogen, are already successfully operating.

Figure 2-9: CAD model of the dedicated vacuum facility.

Figure 2-10: Left – Main chamber and related pumping system installed in the new laboratory. Right – Auxiliary chamber, connected to the main chamber through the gate valve.

The test facility is completed by the automated control system, the thrust balance and the new signal conditioning unit for Faraday and RPA plasma probes, designed and assembled by the Collesalvetti laboratory design team. A sketch of the diagnostics configuration is presented in Fig. 2-11.

Figure 2-11: Side view showing the movable thrust balance and plume diagnostic arm.

In December 2025, the Aerospazio facility was prepared for full-scale test article integration. Collaborative teams from Airbus FHN, TLS, and ELC, and the University of Pisa successfully installed the thruster and fluidic assemblies onto the thrust balance, alongside the breadboard PPU and associated diagnostic suites. Following an initial pumpdown, the vacuum system underwent targeted modifications in early January 2026 to optimize iodine pumping speeds, achieving the high-capacity throughput required for the 3–5 kW power range.

The first integrated coupling tests of the complete subsystem were conducted between mid-January and early February 2026, culminating in the successful ignition of the thruster on iodine propellant, shown in Fig. 2-12.

Figure 2-12: First operation of the whole coupled subsystem at Aerospazio with iodine.

Due to a loss of isolation between the Cathode Reference Potential (CRP) and ground on the PPU side, further testing was prevented. However, it demonstrated that the PPU's safety architecture

functioned as intended by isolating an electrical fault within a specific safety circuit, successfully protecting the core system electronics. Following the repair and recertification of the safety cassette, testing will be resumed.

2.6. University of Pisa: Iodine Flow Sensor Development

Propellant mass flow rate is a critical parameter for the characterization of iodine electric propulsion systems; however, conventional gas mass flow meters are generally unsuitable due to the corrosive nature of iodine. Traditional methods often rely on measuring reservoir mass changes before and after testing [3], a process that lacks the real-time data necessary for precise characterization. As part of the activities for development of iodine propellant management technologies, initiated in 2015, the University of Pisa designed and realized a mass flow meter specific for iodine vapour, based on spectrophotometric techniques, able to perform real time measurements [4, 5].

The device, connected in series with the iodine fluid line, consists of a spectrophotometric cell situated upstream of a capillary pipe sized to maintain sonic conditions at its outlet. The concentration of iodine vapor within the cell is determined by the attenuation of a laser beam at a 520 nm wavelength, corresponding to the maximum absorbance of the iodine molecule. In accordance with the Beer-Lambert Law, the measured absorbance relates linearly to the vapor density and, following proper thermal calibration of the throttle, provides a direct correlation to the instantaneous mass flow rate. The schematic of the device is presented in Fig. 2-13, while the engineering prototype is shown in Fig. 2-14.

Figure 2-13: Schematic of the iodine mass flow meter.

Figure 2-14: Engineering prototype of the iodine mass flow meter.

The MFM was designed to meet the specific requirements of the iFACT-MP project, ensuring accuracy across the entire operational range. The final prototype features a ceramic main body constructed from MACOR, which supports the optical lines, laser source, beam splitter, and photodiodes, while integrated heaters and an electronics board manage telemetry and control. All materials were selected based on proven iodine compatibility through rigorous exposure testing [6].

During preliminary characterization at the University of Pisa, the system was equipped with thermocouples to verify thermal uniformity across the ceramic body, ensuring that the electronics remained within acceptable temperature ranges during extended high-vacuum operation. Measurements on the electronics board showed that all the components of the board remained within the acceptable temperature ranges.

After assessing the thermal behaviour of the system, the reliable operation of the electronics board under high vacuum conditions was verified, checking the linearity and the absence of drift in the absorbance measurement.

Calibration of the system was achieved by correlating the integrated absorbance signal with the mass of iodine captured in activated carbon chemical traps. This methodology is more detailed in [5].

The system was connected to an iodine feeding system which consists of a tank, an isolation valve and a pipe, all of which are thermally regulated using a PID controller. By heating the MFM body to a set temperature and activating the flow for measured intervals, a calibration constant of 0.3834 was derived to relate the instantaneous absorbance and temperature signals to the mass flow rate. The calibration curve is shown in Fig. 2-15.

Figure 2-15: Calibration curve of the MFM, correlating the instantaneous absorbance and temperature signal and the mass flow rate.

Further validation was conducted at the Airbus FHN laboratory, where the MFM was interfaced with an iodine tank and proportional valve. These tests confirmed a correlation between valve opening settings and instantaneous flow values for flow rates below 2 mg/s, shown in Fig. 2-16. The reliability of the measurement was further verified by monitoring a secondary backup carbon vial, which showed no weight gain, confirming total iodine capture during the calibration process. The vial is shown in Fig. 2-17.

Figure 2-16: Iodine flowrate vs time plot. Tank temperature: 95°C. Proportional valve and MFM temperature: 90°C. Proportional valve current: A) 170 mA, B) 170 mA, C) 170 mA, D) 180 mA, E) 150 mA, F) 160 mA, G) 190 mA, H) 200 mA.

Figure 2-17: Appearance of vials after iodine collection.

In December 2025, the MFM was integrated into the iodine fluidic chain provided by Airbus TLS upstream of the thruster unit on the Aerospazio thrust balance. In the first firing attempts in January 2026, no iodine flow could be generated, therefore the MFM was removed from the iodine fluidic chain to reduce the pressure drop across the feeding. Further investigation is necessary to prepare the MFM for the 500-endurance test.

2.7. EASN-TIS: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

The iFACT-MP team recognizes the critical importance of launching dissemination and communication activities early in the project’s lifecycle to generate interest, strengthen the project’s impact, and build a broad, engaged community.

EASN-TIS spearheads the project's Dissemination & Communication (D&C) efforts. The D&C team has developed a dynamic and continually updated plan to share information and raise awareness about the project’s objectives. Dissemination focuses on effectively delivering the project’s results to relevant professional and scientific audiences, while communication is designed to inform and captivate a broader, non-specialist audience.

To support these aims, EASN-TIS has produced and distributed a suite of D&C tools, including the official project logo, customizable deliverable templates, and the Initial Communication Toolkit (ICT), featuring both a trifold leaflet and a poster.

EASN-TIS has also implemented an automated approval process, the Dissemination e-Approval Tool, to streamline dissemination activity oversight and minimize intellectual property (IP) conflicts. This online platform has successfully managed the approval process for two scientific papers to date. Furthermore, the iFACT-MP project has established a presence on LinkedIn and launched its official website, ifact-mp.eu, further expanding its visibility and accessibility.

In addition to these traditional outreach tools, the project has introduced compelling audiovisual series and iodine-focused media content to further enhance its outreach efforts:

- “Ask the Researchers!” video series: A brand-new multimedia initiative featured on YouTube, where project researchers discuss their work, share insights, and answer viewer questions. This dynamic approach offers a more personal and engaging window into the project and its developments.
- Iodine-Centric Content: The website also hosts a section titled “Iodine, Thrusters & Thoughts”, which explores topics related to iodine-fed electric propulsion systems, including technical, scientific, and conceptual perspectives. This new storytelling series brings our audience closer to the minds and personalities shaping the future of space technology.

Some material created by EASN-TIS is presented in Fig. 2-18.

Figure 2-18: Materials published to communicate the progress and results, including leaflets, fact sheets, newsletters, a video series about the consortium partners' contributions, and "Iodine, Thrusters & Thoughts" LinkedIn series presenting individual team member.

3. CONCLUSION

The iFACT-MP project has achieved several critical milestones in the development of a 3–5 kW hybrid propulsion subsystem.

Key accomplishments include the successful design and functional validation of the thruster unit, which demonstrated stable operation in its baseline krypton configuration. Significant progress was also made in advancing iodine-specific technologies, including a fluidic chain for reliable propellant delivery, a versatile breadboard PPU for autonomous control, an in-situ optical mass flow meter, and the availability of Europe's largest iodine compatible test facility with state-of-the-art diagnostics.

The project has also made progress in developing an iodine-fed cathode using enhanced C12A7 emitters with higher melting point, although stable operation with iodine could not be achieved yet. Some key performance parameters are listed in Table 3-1.

While the initial coupling tests and iodine ignition were successful at Aerospazio, the transition to the final qualification phase encountered technical difficulties with a ground-test specific protective circuit which impacted the project timeline. Following the resolution of associated safety hardware, the endurance test campaign is planned to resume in Q2 2026.

Table 3-1: Summarized results of the iFACT-MP project.

Sub-system	Parameter	Target value	Actual value
Thruster	PTTR	< 25 W/mN	Noble gas: 20-35 W/mN
			Iodine: Char. ongoing
	Isp	> 1800 s	Noble gas: up to 1860 s
			Iodine: Char. ongoing
Cathode	Ignition voltage	< 100 V	> 96 V
	C12A7 emitter melting point	> 1400 °C	1450°C
Fluidic	Throttle response time	< 3 s	<1 s
	Max. iodine flow rate	> 10 mg/s	no full-scale MFM char. yet
PPU	Max. output power	5 kW	10 kW
	Anode voltage range	300 - 700 V	0-800 V
Flow Sensor	Accuracy	< 5 %	5 %
	Acquisition rate	< 1 Hz	1-10 Hz
Test facility	Testable iodine thruster power level	> 3 kW	3.6 kW tested

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